

Photo(electro)catalytic conversion of CO₂ over Cu₂O/MXene composites

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In photo(electro)chemical conversion of carbon dioxide, the copper(I)oxide (Cu₂O) has gained a great interest as the main component of photocathode for photo(electro)chemical (PEC) reduction of CO₂ due to its narrow band gap and suitable band alignment. Heterostructures integrating low-dimensional materials with Cu₂O (*p*-type of semiconductor) can provide enhanced optoelectronic properties. New family of two-dimensional transition metal carbides, so called MXenes, has attracted a great attention due to their excellent metallic conductivity, high volumetric capacitance, and hydrophilic surfaces. MXene Ti₃C₂T_x has good prerequisites to improve the performance of Cu₂O as photocathode for CO₂ reduction – suitable Fermi level and easy transformation into thin Ti₃C₂T_x covered with TiO₂ (*n*-type of semiconductor) [1].

In this contribution, we present results on CO₂ PEC reduction with multicomponent FTO/Cu₂O/Ti₃C₂T_x photocathode. The effect of multilayered Ti₃C₂T_x and multilayered Ti₃C₂T_x covered with TiO₂ on the charge transfer, the overall stability of photocathode and product selectivity will be discussed.

Figure 1: Energy diagram of Cu₂O, TiO₂ and multilayered MXene Ti₃C₂T_x.

Keywords: photo(electro)catalytic CO₂ reduction, MXenes, copper oxides

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References

[1] J. Low et al., *Journal of Catalysis*, **361** 255 (2018).